

The results are in Table 2.

Nutrient accumulation due to straw incorporation, averaged for the three water regimes, was as follows:

Nutrient	kg/ha per season
Total N	38
Available P	3
Exchangeable K	11

In 2 parallel 6-year-long field experiments, incorporation of straw produced in situ gave the identical value of 38 kg/ha per season for nitrogen added. Although the content of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium increased, yield was low with or without straw incorporation and the benefit of straw incorporation small because of zinc

deficiency and boron toxicity induced by bad irrigation water.

To ascertain whether comparable amounts of nutrients were added in other soils, the effect of straw incorporation at 5 t/ha on the nutrient status of three soils was studied outdoors in 200-liter steel drums. The soils were Luisiana clay (pH: 6.7, total N: 0.154%), Maahas clay (pH: 7.1, total N: 0.130%), and Pila clay loam (pH: 7.7, total N: 0.109%).

Nitrogen accretion varied with the soil: it was highest in Pila clay loam and least in Maahas clay. In all three soils straw incorporation significantly increased grain yield (Table 3). The increase in nutrient content on a hectare basis was as follows:

Clay	Increase (kg/ha per season)		
	Total N	Available P	Exchangeable K
Luisiana clay	43	0.3	13
Maahas clay	26	0.2	24
Pila clay loam	77	1.0	17
Mean	49	0.5	18

Incorporation of straw brought about an increase of 38 kg nitrogen and about 14 kg/ha per season of exchangeable potassium in two field experiments on Maahas clay. The corresponding increases averaged for three soils in a drum study were 49 kg N and 18 kg K.

Incorporating straw increases the natural supply of nutrients in wetland rice soils. ■

Efficient use of fertilizer nitrogen in wetland rice under poor water management

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A split application of nitrogen sometimes increases fertilizer efficiency and yields of wetland rice more than does a single basal application. But the efficiency of split-applied nitrogen depends on water management. Water-management constraints in farmers' fields include field-to-field irrigation, lack of drainage facilities, and over irrigation prompted by irregular water supply. Therefore the practice of split nitrogen application was evaluated under both controlled and uncontrolled irrigation in the 1978 wet season in five villages under the Operational Research Project, Miryalguda, Andhra Pradesh. The soil was a red sandy loam with pH 7.8-8.0 and 0.52-0.86% organic matter. Controlled irrigation (CI) involved submergence at 2- to 5-cm level through separate channels, drainage before topdressing of nitrogen, and reflooding. Uncontrolled irrigation (UI) practices were the farmers' normal heavy application of irrigation water (submergence level varying from 5 to 20 cm), field-to-field irrigation, and topdressing of nitrogen on

Effect of water management on grain yield and efficiency of urea-nitrogen applied at 100 kg N/ha. Mean of 5 experimental sites in a farmer's field. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1978 wet season.^a

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		Yield response (kg grain/kg fertilizer N)		Recovery of fertilizer N in grain + straw (%) (Differential method)	
	CI ^b	UI ^b	CI	UI	CI	UI
Control, no N	3.6	3.1	—	—	—	—
Urea, 3 splits	6.0	4.4	23.2	13.4	40.3	21.9
NC-urea, 3 splits	6.0	4.9	23.0	18.2	29.4	24.7
NC-urea, all basal	6.7	5.6	30.7	25.1	65.9	46.5
LSD (0.05)	0.66		7.80		9.08	
CV (%)	10.00		16.50		18.05	

^a NC-urea = urea blended with neem cake (residue of *Azadirachta indica* seed after oil extraction) at 30% by weight of urea using coal tar solution. Split application = 25% basal with incorporation, 50% topdressed at active tillering stage and 25% at panicle initiation.

^b CI = controlled irrigation, UI = uncontrolled irrigation.

floodwater with no previous drainage.

All treatments required careful water management for best results (see table).

Yields decreased about 26% when split application of ordinary urea was associated with the farmers' poor management of irrigation water.

Despite poor water management, basal application of neem cake-blended urea gave yields, yield responses, and crop recovery of added nitrogen equal to those of split application of ordinary urea under ideal conditions. ■

Effect of seedling age and number per hill on grain yield of rice varieties

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Seedlings of rice varieties Pusa 2-21 and Jaya were transplanted at 20, 40, and 60 days after seeding to study the extent of yield reduction when transplanting

is delayed. To compensate for yield reduction 2, 4, or 6 seedlings/hill were transplanted. The experiment used a randomized block design with four replications. The crop was sown in wet nursery beds at the Crop Research Center, Pantnagar on 16 June in the 1977-78 wet season.

When older seedlings of short-duration Pusa 2-21 were transplanted, yield reduction was consistent regardless of

Effect of age (20, 40, 60 days) and number of seedlings per hill on grain yield of rice varieties, 1977 wet season, Pantnagar, India.

Seedlings (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)					
	Jaya			Pusa 2-21		
	20 d	40 d	60 d	20 d	40 d	60 d
2	6.8	6.5	4.9	7.3	6.0	4.6
4	7.5	5.7	5.7	7.3	6.2	5.2
6	7.4	6.6	5.0	7.4	6.7	5.4

Source of variation	Standard deviation of mean (±)	Coefficient of variation (%)	Coefficient of difference at 5%
Variety	0.3	19	
Seedling age	0.4		1.1
Seedlings/hill	0.4		1.1
Variety × age × seedlings/hill interaction	1.0		2.7

seedling number. The yield increased when the number of seedlings from the same age group rose from 2 to 6/hill (see table). The magnitude of yield reduction due to overaged seedlings was low for the medium-duration Jaya. The yield

increased with 2 and 4 seedlings of the same age group per hill, and 6 seedlings/hill for 40-day-old seedlings. The difference was probably due to a buildup in the insect population in a few plots. ■

Reduction of nursery area in wet cultivation of rice

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A study was conducted at Ambasamudram to determine the minimum area required for a seedbed and the optimum seeding rate.

Seedlings from the nursery seeded at 3, 6, and 9 kg/40 m² were healthier and stronger than those seeded at 12 kg/40 m². The seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m² were taller than those seeded at the other rates. The number of leaves that each seedling produced did not differ among

the various treatments (see table).

When the seed rate was increased from 3 to 6 kg/40 m², the number of seedlings per unit area proportionally increased. When the seed rate was increased to 9 and 12 kg/40 m² the increase in the number of seedlings was not proportional. That might be attributable to the high mortality of seedlings at higher seed rates.

The seedlings from the nursery seeded at 6 kg/40 m², when spaced at 20 × 10 cm, covered twice the main field area covered by the seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m². Increasing the seeding rate to 9 and 12 kg/40 m² did not result in a proportional increase in the main field area covered.

Effect of nursery seeding rate on rice seedlings and wet cultivation of rice, Paddy Experiment Station, Tamil Nadu, India.

Seeding rate (kg/40 m ²)	Seedling ht (cm)	Leaves (no./seedling)	Seedlings (no./m ²)	Area (m ²) covered in the main field with seedlings	Seedbed required to transplant 1 ha main field (m ²)	Transplanting rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
3	30	4	3201	21	480	36	6.2
6	23	4	6024	40	252	38	5.6
9	22	4	6816	45	224	51	5.2
12	22	4	8027	53	188	57	4.9

C.D.: 0.4

However, the yield of seedlings seeded at 6 kg/40 m² was lower (5.6 t/ha) than that of seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m² (6.2 t/ha) (see table). Because yield was the ultimate deciding factor, the nursery seeded at 3 kg/40 m² was the most economically advantageous. ■

Response of transplanted rice to zinc application in Gangetic alluvial soils

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Improved rice varieties planted in alluvial soils often show symptoms of zinc deficiency, particularly during early growth. Zinc deficiency is usually corrected by applying zinc to the soil or as a foliar spray. Therefore, to determine the importance of zinc application to rice production, an experiment was conducted with and without zinc. The zinc was applied at a rate of 16 kg/ha as soil application and 5 kg/ha as a foliar spray in kharif 1976 at the BHU Research Farm. The soil is medium-textured with a pH of 7.3.

Zinc as zinc sulfate was incorporated into the soil at final puddling; it was also sprayed at the tillering and booting growth stages. The effects of the two methods of zinc application on plant height, straw yield, and grain yield components were compared.

The experiment showed that alluvial soils are deficient in available zinc. Zinc application increased grain and straw yield significantly. Foliar-sprayed zinc increased yield by 17.2%; it also increased straw yield and 100-grain weight. Both soil and foliar application of zinc significantly affected plant height and number of grains per panicle. ■

Nitrogen management at moderate levels of nitrogen in lowland rice

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A field experiment on nitrogen